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The Implementation of the Education and Training Policy of 2014 (2023 Edition) on Library Resources Strategies for Competence-Based Education: A Case of the Evangelical Lutheran Church in Tanzania, Northern Diocese Secondary Schools, Hai District in Kilimanjaro Region

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ABSTRACT: This article is rooted in the Education and Training Policy (ETP) 2014 (2023) Edition on the availability and enhancement of library services for Competence-Based Education (CBE). The study context is the Evangelical Lutheran Church in Tanzania (ELCT) Northern Diocese (ND) secondary schools in Hai District, Kilimanjaro Region. The specific objective was to assess strategies used to enhance library resources. The study employed a qualitative research approach with a case study design and a sample size of 31 participants. Interviews, questionnaires, observations, and document reviews were used to collect data. Researchers used thematic analysis techniques to analyze the data. The social constructivism theory navigated the study. The findings revealed that strategies for enhancing library resources include the independent learning method, provision of hard and soft study materials, allocation of a timetable for students' library sessions, and the use of a project-based learning method. The study concluded that the student-centric approach to teaching and learning, combined with social-interactive library management practices, supports the use of library resources. The positive utilization of strategies is recommended for library users and library management practices to accommodate modern changes.

KEYWORDS: competence-based education, training policy of 2014 (2023 edition), Evangelical Lutheran Church in Tanzania, Northern Diocese, library resources, strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several factors, including the provision of library resources, determine the quality of education and training. Other factors include the quality of the curriculum, the proficiency of curriculum implementers, leadership, management, the learning environment, and assessment (MoEST, 2023a; Joseph, 2010; Dillon, 2009). In practice, these factors are interdependent and mutually reliant to achieve positive outcomes in education and training (MoEST, 2023a; Joseph, 2010; Dillon, 2009). In Tanzania, as in other countries, quality library services have been identified as teaching and learning resources that contribute to the development of knowledge, skills, and positive attitudes essential for achieving success in academic and real-life situations (Pandey, 2024; MoEST, 2023a; Sakhrekar et al., 2021; Namocot et al., 2021). In this era of science and technology, library resources are designed to support their users, including students, in shifting the focus of teaching and learning from the traditional teacher-centered approach, which emphasizes content delivery, to a more active, student-centered approach. The emphasis is placed on outcomes, specifically students' ability to demonstrate their learning through practical application and competence (MoEST, 2023a; Tshabalala et al., 2023; Sakhrekar et al., 2021; Namocot et al., 2021; Care et al., 2018; Simmonds, 2014).

This study focuses on Competence-Based Education, which emphasizes the development of skills, knowledge, and attitudes essential for achieving success in real-life situations. In Tanzania, CBE has been identified as a critical aspect of educational reform. The Tanzania Education and Training Policy 2014 (2023) Edition emphasizes the need for a curriculum that develops competencies in students, including problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts (MoEST, 2023a).

Regarding library resources, these are teaching-learning resources that were initiated as one of the main themes identified in the reviewed ETP 2014 (2023) Edition. This theme included various policy statements to guide the implementation of the identified theme and help meet its objectives. Sections 3.3 and 3.6.4 of the policy describe these resources, which include ICT infrastructure, sufficient high-quality books and materials, digital learning tools and equipment, as well as physical infrastructure such as classrooms and laboratories (MoEST, 2023a). Thus, the success of CBE relies heavily on the availability of suitable teaching and learning resources (MoEST, 2023a). Regarding the concepts of CBE and library resources, educational strategies are purposeful, coherent, and adaptive plans of action composed of sequenced instructional activities,

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resource utilization, and reflective decision-making, designed to accomplish long-term learning objectives within specific contexts (Oxman et al., 2025). Thus, for this study, strategies are understood as plans or ways through which library resources could be utilized to enhance Competence-Based Education in secondary schools.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Social Constructivism Theory

The Social Constructivism theory is a theory developed in the 1920s to 1930s by Lev Vygotsky, a prominent soviet psychologist and educator. In the book titled "Basic of Learning the Latest Theories and Methods" by Nino 2023. The social constructivist sees knowledge as what students do in collaboration with other students, teachers and peers. Teachers provide instructional assistance by utilizing teaching and learning materials and methods that allow students to find and create knowledge as they engage and collaborate during the learning process. The key elements of the theory are active learning, learner-centered, emphasis on prior knowledge, social interaction, problem-solving. Nevertheless, the Social Constructivism theory is highly relevant to enhance competence-based education. This is because the theory viewed learning as a social process in where students participated through group activities to facilitate meaningful learning. Teachers provided instructional assistance by employing teaching strategies that allow students to explore and develop knowledge as they interact and collaborate during the learning process.

2.2 Discussion and Analysis of Previous Studies

Regarding literature related to the use of library resources for CBE, several researchers have contributed to the understanding of related practices in various ways. Pandey (2024) conducted an extensive literature review to explore the role of knowledge management in enhancing library services in India. Knowledge management is a systematic approach that organizations use to identify, create, capture, organize, store, share, and leverage the knowledge and expertise of their personnel to improve efficiency, decision-making, and innovation (Pandey, 2024; Olmstead, 2022). The study found that effective knowledge management practices are essential in enhancing library services.

Additionally, knowledge management promotes a culture of ongoing learning and growth among library personnel, enabling them to adapt to evolving user needs and technological advancements. One of the recommendations made in this study was that libraries can effectively leverage existing management structures and technology to implement successful library management strategies. Furthermore, Sakhrekar et al. (2023) conducted a mixed-methods research study on library facilities, examining their importance, problems, and expectations. The study's findings were quantified based on the expectations of library users, the library environment, key issues affecting the library, evaluation of library performance, and communication with the library management team. The study concluded that library users demand more comfort while studying in the library; therefore, library management should strengthen its structure and practices.

Furthermore, a quantitative study was conducted by Mojapelo (2018) on challenges in establishing and maintaining functional school libraries: lessons from Limpopo Province, South Africa. The study is evident that there are daunting challenges that hinder the effective establishment and maintenance of a functional school library and information service. The study recommended that the National Department of Basic Education has a responsibility to ensure that the school library policy is formulated, endorsed, and implemented. Additionally, the Government must expedite the rural development of libraries.

In addition, Fankule (2023) conducted a quantitative study about the availability and utilization of school library resources for learning activities by students in selected secondary schools in Nigeria. Findings revealed that dictionaries, textbooks, encyclopedias, CD-ROMs, and novels were very available for use by secondary school students. Additionally, the primary purposes for which secondary school students utilize information resources were for assignments, preparation for continuous assessments, knowledge updates, competitions, and quiz preparation. However, awareness of the library's information resources, the employment of computer technicians for routine repairs, the provision of digital libraries, the adequate provision of online computers and email, and the provision of standby generators for regular power supply were significant factors that promoted the use of information resources by secondary school students.

Likewise, Bernard and Dulle (2014) conducted a mixed-methods study to assess the access to and use of school library information resources by secondary school students in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. The key findings indicated that the most frequently used library information resources by the students are only books and novels. Other resources available in the library, such as atlases, maps, dictionaries, audio-visual materials, and poetry, were not accessible to students; therefore, these resources were not satisfactory in meeting their information needs. Additionally, the study highlighted challenges encountered by the students when using school libraries. These are: the absence of current and up-to-date reading materials, limited reading hours, insufficient seating, and a lack of professional information personnel. Additionally, Malekani and Mabofu (2019) examined the challenges of school libraries and the quality of education in Tanzania. The argument was put forward that more awareness of the link between school libraries and quality education should be communicated, particularly to government officials. This is because challenges such as staffing, funding, the lack of standard library buildings, and the frequent change of curricula need to be addressed by the Government for better quality education in the country.

As for the current study, MoEST initiates the link between library services and the enhancement of CBE. This is well stipulated in section 3.6.4.6 of the ETP 2014 (2023) Edition. The policy states that:

The Government, in collaboration with stakeholders, will ensure the availability and enhancement of library services and alternative knowledge acquisition methods in schools, colleges, and communities to promote a culture of reading.

Since the revised Education and Training Policy (ETP) of 2014 (2023) is currently in effect, this study investigated the reality of implementing the mentioned statement by ELCT ND secondary schools in Hai District.

The reviewed literature broadened our knowledge of studies focusing on library information resources in general, and particularly in the school context. Apart from differences in research contexts where the studies were conducted, various research methodologies were employed, mainly the mixed methods research approach (Kamwera et al., 2024; Fankule, 2023; Sakhrekar et al., 2023; Namocot et al., 2021; Majapelo, 2018; Benard & Dulle, 2014). Additionally, the qualitative research approach, in the form of a literature review, was primarily used to gather in-depth information

(Pandey, 2024; Malekani & Mabofu, 2019). Most of the recommendations were directed at government officials and school administrators as ways to address some of the challenges identified in library resources and practices. The existing study focused on the implementation of the policy statement on the availability and use of library resources for CBE. The policy statements were officially implemented in 2024, following the approval of the current ETP (MoEST, 2023a). Further, the context of the current study is within private secondary schools. The approach undertaken was qualitative, informed by the social constructivist theory, which emphasizes a collaborative nature in facilitating knowledge. The current study examined a notable gap in the implementation of the policy statement. There is a lack of published empirical studies on the strategies employed by these private schools to enhance library resources for CBE. If the problem is not investigated, the intended improvements in educational outcomes may not be realized. Although the Tanzanian Government and educational stakeholders have developed frameworks for resource allocation and pedagogical tools under competence-based education, the practical application of this policy statement in private schools remains under-researched.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach and Design

The study employed a qualitative research approach, guided by a case study design (Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Mugenyi & Mokoro, 2022; Alikhan et al., 2023). The research approach was crucial for this study, as it determined the methodology for investigating library use in Competence-Based Education. The approach also seeks to explore experiences, perceptions, and practices that cannot be easily quantified due to the nature of this study. A case study design was employed to investigate the specific context of the ELCT Northern Diocese secondary schools in Hai District. This design enabled the researchers to focus on the study's objective and question, determine methods for collecting and analyzing the data, and describe the criteria for processing the data that ensured trustworthiness and addressed ethical considerations for the study.

3.2 Area of Study, Population, and Sampling

This study involved five private secondary schools owned by the ELCT Northern Diocese in Hai District, Kilimanjaro Region. Hai District appeared to have a rich institutional structure, with Hai Province being a reasonable fit for the study due to two reasons: it accommodates more secondary schools owned by the ELCT ND compared to other Provinces under the proximity of the ND, which are Karatu, Siha, Central, and Kilimanjaro East. Additionally, there is a literature gap regarding several challenges encountered by library resources, as reported by scholars reviewed in this study. The study's targeted population consisted of 76 individuals. The total sample size was 31 participants. The purposive expert sampling technique was used to choose participants based on their knowledge and skills relevant to the study (Friday & Leah, 2024; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Mungenyi & Mokoro, 2022). In-depth information was collected from 5 Heads of School, 5 Academic Masters/Mistresses, 5 School Bursars, 5 Heads of ICT Departments, 5 Heads of Arts Departments, 5 Heads of Sciences Departments, and 1 Education Secretary of the ELCT ND secondary schools.

3.3 Methods for Data Collection and Analysis

The study collected data through interviews, questionnaires, observations, and document review (Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Ruslin et al., 2022; Kumar, 2023; Kutsyuruba, 2023; Kuphanga, 2024). These instruments enabled the participants and researchers to provide detailed information on the strategies employed by the schools under study to enhance the use of library resources in a competence-based teaching and learning environment. Thus, interviews were conducted with the Heads of school and the Educational Secretary of the ELCT ND. The interview guide was structured to include both open-ended and closed-ended questions. The questions were asked in a manner that allowed the interviewee to gain a broad understanding of library use in their schools.

Furthermore, questionnaires were distributed to Academic Masters, school Bursars, and Heads of the Departments of ICT, Arts, and Science. The questionnaires were structured similarly to the interview guide, with the addition of a section on other issues that could support strategies for enhancing library resources to initiate CBE. Furthermore, the researchers use an observation checklist that guides the observation of teaching and learning resources, including computers, projectors, tablets, library staff, textbooks, classrooms, and laboratories. In addition, several documents were reviewed to enrich the data. The documents include the ELCT strategic plan for 2024-2028, the schools' strategic plans for 2024-2028, the schools' work plan for 2024 and 2025, schemes of work, lesson plans, and the timetable. The gathered data were analyzed thematically (Cohen et al., 2018). Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the textual data from the research instruments mentioned in order to uncover the underlying meanings, themes, and patterns within the data.

3.4 Trustworthiness of the Data

The trustworthiness of the study was established to ensure that the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability were adhered to (Braun & Clarke, 2023; Yanto, 2023; Hag et al., 2023). In this study, credibility was ensured by employing four methods to collect data from participants who were implementing the studied statement on teaching and learning to enhance competence-based education. The transferability of the current study addresses the growing societal need for an education system that equips students with the necessary competencies. The criteria for dependability considered in this qualitative study employed various methodologies and theories that assisted in collecting data for the study, which cannot easily be quantified. Lastly, confirmability was ensured through reflexivity and by discussing the data, considering the research objective and the question, which enabled the researcher to obtain findings for the study.

3.5 Research Ethics

During the conduct of this study, research ethics were adhered to at all stages (Arafat, 2024; Creswell & Creswell, 2023). The researchers obtained an official introductory letter from the office of the Director for Postgraduate Studies at Tumaoni Makumira University (TUMA). Thereafter, the official permission letter from TUMA granted access to obtain official permission from the ELCT ND Head Office to conduct research in their five secondary schools in Hai District. Several key ethical principles guided the researchers in considering Christian-Lutheran practices in daily routines, provided participants with informed consent forms, and utilized a plagiarism checker tool to verify the integrity of the entire research (Kang, 2023; Soundararajan, 2022).

4. RESULTS

The findings section presents the data collected through interviews, questionnaires, observation, and document review to assess the strategies employed by the schools under study in Hai District to enhance the use of library resources for CBE. In this section, the schools involved in the study are identified as SSC-1 through SSC-5. The participants are named HoS, SSC-1, which means the Head of School from Secondary School 1 up to HoS, SSC-5. Furthermore, the Education Secretary is referred to as EDS. The Academic Master from Secondary School 1 is named ACM, SSC-1 up to ACM, SSC-5. The Heads of Department were identified as follows: HoDICT, SSC-1 to SSC-5; HoD Arts, SSC-1 to SSC-5; and HoD Sc, SSC-1 to SSC-5. Additionally, School Bursars were involved and designated as Burs, ranging from Burs, SSC-1 to Burs, SSC-5. The results section is divided into two main sections and several sub-sections.

4.1 Data Collection Tools Return Rate

The data collection tools return rate of participants involved in this study as presented in Table 1. The data were collected from 31 participants from SSC-1 up to SSC-5. The data collection tools returned rate is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Data Collection Tools Return Rate (N=31)

Data Collection Tools	Participants Category	Targeted F	Participated F	Percentage %
Questionnaire	Academic master	5	5	100
	Heads of departments (ICT, Arts, Sc)	15	15	100
	School bursars	5	5	100
TOTAL		25	25	100%

Source: Field Data, 2025

The data in Table 1. shows 100% of the participants of the data collection tools return rate. From interview, all planned 6 participants were participated for 100%. Habiyu and Njuguna (2025) report that 75% of tools return rate is enough for the study. From the study, the participants participated for 100%. This allowed the researcher to proceed with data analysis processes as the percentage obtained were above 75%.

4.2 Background Characteristics of Participants

The background characteristics of the participants involved in this study include gender, education qualification, and working experience in years. Table 2 shows the participants' background characteristics.

Table 2 : Background Characteristics of Participants

Demographic Category	Intervals	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Gender	Female	4	12.9
	Male	27	87.1
	TOTAL	31	100
Education Qualification	Diploma	3	9.7
	Bachelor	25	80.6
	Master	3	9.7
	TOTAL	31	100
Working Experiences	Less than 1 year	1	3.2
	1-5 years	14	45.2
	6-10 years	7	22.5
	11-15 years	3	9.7
	16-20 years	3	9.7
	Over 20 years	3	9.7
	TOTAL	31	100

Source: Field Data, 2025

The data in Table 2. shows that a researcher used a total of 31 participants where by majority of them were males (87.1%) and minority of them were females (12.9%) in terms of gender. This implies that most of teachers are males, possibly due to geographical reasons. These schools are

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mostly located in rural areas where some females could find impossible to travel daily with their families. Also, Participants were characterized into four groups. based on the aspect of educational qualifications, (9.7%) of research participants were holding a diploma, (80.6%) holding a bachelor's degree, and (9.7%) holding a master's degree. This means that the majority of secondary school teachers are skilled due to their high degree of education.

Furthermore, the data in Table 1 demonstrate that 14 (45.2%) of the participants had 1-5 years of work experience implementing the policy statements. Furthermore, 7 (22.5%) of the participants had 6-10 years of working experience, 3 (9.7%) of the participants had 11-15 years of working experience, 3 (9.7%) of the participants had 16-20 years of working experience, and 3 (9.7%) of the participants had more than 20 years of working experiences. This means that, the involved participants were highly experienced in teaching and could be possible to implement the policy statements effectively.

Generally, the data on the demographic information of the participants who participated in this study in terms of response return rate, gender, and education qualification, working experience in years enhance trustworthiness of the phenomena being studied.

4.3 Library Resources Strategies for Competence-Based Education

This study aimed to assess the strategies employed by the ELCT ND secondary schools in Hai District to enhance the utilization of library resources in support of Competence-Based Education. The findings revealed four strategies that enhance the use of library resources as a means of practicing CBE: the independent learning method, provision of hard and soft study materials, a timetable for students' library sessions, and the project-based learning method, as presented below.

Independent Learning Method

An independent learning method was mentioned and explained as a strategy for enhancing the use of library resources to instill competence-based education. The researchers observed the following: Students were given a task that required them to search for materials on tablets and in the library. Librarians facilitated these students' search for materials and helped them find a seat individually, allowing them to continue studying comfortably. However, some students returned to the librarian for inquiries (Observation by the researchers, SSC-5 on March 3, 2025). Similarly, the HoS, SSC-5 informed that;

As a school, students use the library for individual learning. The school also utilizes a movable library to encourage many students to engage in reading for various purposes. This is the best way for students to develop critical thinking, share ideas, and materials, which facilitate learning. Additionally, the school utilizes tablets that contain all the necessary library materials for learning, and students can access these tablets while in the library (Interview with HoS, SSC-5, on March 3, 2025).

Likewise, the ACM from SSC-5 informed that "teachers often guide students on how to prepare notes or summaries from library resources by emphasizing critical reading and integrating multiple sources" (Questionnaire with Academic Master, SSC-5, March 3, 2025).

The data on independent-based learning as a strategy for utilizing library resources suggests that the students in the studied schools are at the center of the teaching and learning process. Thus, the libraries become conducive environment for practicing competence-based teaching and learning when its resources are utilized.

Provision of Hard and Soft Study Materials

The data from various tools indicate that subject textbooks prepared by the Tanzania Institute of Education (TIE) are available in both hard and soft copies, which are sufficient for teaching and learning. The researchers observed that Form One students were discussing and sharing ideas from the English Language students' book prepared by the TIE. Form One students were studying how to use ICT tools to search for information (Observation from researchers-SSC-2 on March 3, 2025). The researchers observed that these textbooks are very communicative. This is because they include photos, instructions, questions, and explanations that can assist students in learning more effectively, even as individuals (Observation by the researchers, SSC-2 on March 3, 2025, and SSC-4 on March 4, 2025).

Through interviews, one among the Heads of schools said that "availability of books, for example, the current TIE books are very interesting with current information" (Interview with HoS, SSC-2 on March 3, 2025). Similarly, the Educational Secretary was of the view that "we encourage our schools to use current books to modernize facilities in the library for students and teachers" (Interview with EDS on March 12, 2025). Also, ACM SSC-4 commented that "ensuring teachers to develop and share digital lessons" (Questionnaire from ACM on March 4, 2025). The use of "internet browsers to search for materials" (Questionnaire from ICT HoD SSC-3 on March 7, 2025). Also, the Sc HoD commented that, "encouraging students to use ICT to conduct projects and collaborative tasks" (Questionnaire from SC HoD SSC-1 on March 10, 2025). The data on the strategy for providing hard and soft study materials for teaching and learning suggests that ICT tools are essential in modernizing library services. This is possible when teachers and students can access both hard and soft study materials for teaching and learning.

Timetable for Students' Library Sessions

The researchers observed that all five schools involved in this study have libraries and librarians. In these schools the timetable for library sessions are allocated on the notes board which show time for different classes to use the library (Observation by the researchers, SSC-3 on March 7, 2025) and through document review, the researchers reviewed the school timetable for students library sessions at SSC-3 on March 7, 2025 & SSC-5 on March 3, 2025). Through interviews with HoS, it was reported that "the school makes sure that the librarian is available to help students and teachers who need library services, which are given in different sessions for different classes" (Interview with HoS, SSC-5 on March 3, 2025). Another HoS said that "Our school, through internal and external auditors, monitors and evaluates teaching and learning resources like library resources... This enables our school to purchase and place relevant materials in the library ..." (Interview with SSC-2 on March 3, 2025).

The data from questionnaires also shows that timetabling library sessions is important, as indicated by the statement "students to have a timetable for library learning" (Questionnaire from Burs, SSC-2 & SSC-5 on March 3, 2025). Additionally, "conducting sessions for students to be familiar with library services" (Questionnaires from Sc HoD, SSC-3, on March 7, 2025).

The data above suggests that when students and teachers at the ELCT ND secondary schools in Hai District are familiar with library services, they are more likely to use the library. Therefore, it is essential to schedule library sessions for various classes to ensure the library can accommodate its users effectively.

Project-Based Learning Method

During the observation, the researchers noted that Form Four students were assigned to prepare project proposals for gardening, taking into account the school environment. Through this process, students reviewed various library materials and shared ideas in groups before writing a project proposal on gardening (Observation from researchers SSC-4 on March 4, 2025). Moreover, researchers observed in another school that Form Four and Form Two students were assigned a project from the Agriculture subject (Observation from researchers, SSC-1, on March 10, 2025). Furthermore, during interviews with HoS, it was informed that;

Through online sources, students can access library resources to support assignments, research reports, and projects that require these materials.

By aligning continuous assessment with library resources, students are not only motivated to utilize the library's offerings but also foster a deeper understanding of the subject matter and are encouraged to develop effective research strategies. This strategy helps students recognize the value of the library in their academic journey. Additionally, by fostering critical thinking skills through online sources, students can easily access a wide range of library materials (Interview with HoS-SSC-4 on March 4, 2025).

Another participant said that, "in our school, teachers are encouraged to design assignments in such a way that demand students to conduct discussion, projects that direct them to use scholarly sources, books, and journals available in the library" (Interview with HoS-SSC-3 on March 7, 2025).

Regarding enhancing competence-based teaching and learning, HoS, SSC-4 said that "Student-centered learning approach is more emphasized in schools, whereby teachers guide and facilitate students during the teaching and learning process" (Interview with HoS, SSC-4 on March 4, 2025).

The data on strategies for enhancing the use of library resources suggests that the project-based learning method provides an opportunity for teachers and students at the ELCT Northern Diocese in Hai District to engage in competence-based education.

5. DISCUSSION

This section discusses the key findings on the strategies used to enhance library resources for CBE. The study originated from the policy statement, stipulated in Section 3.6.4.6 of the 2014 (2023) Edition of the ETP, regarding the availability and enhancement of library services to support CBE. The study found that the policy statement was implemented in schools that were involved in the study. Library services are also available. Thus, the discussion focuses on two main themes: student-centric approaches to teaching and learning methods, as well as school library management practices.

Student-Centric Approach to Teaching and Learning Methods

Two main strategies have emerged under the theme of student-centric approach to teaching and learning methods that enhance the use of library resources for CBE. These methods are individual learning and project-based learning. The methods enable students to be self-accountable for their learning. This is because the student is the center of teaching and learning. A student-centered teaching and learning method require a student to become the focal point of teaching and learning (Fufa et al., 2023). The following steps outline a student-centered approach.

Individual Learning Method

In this study, the individual learning method is also understood as independently performing learning tasks, which encourages students to study using their preferred learning style and utilize skills they have already acquired (Karpenko et al., 2019). This strategy is also supported by Mashingia (2023), who assessed the implementation of practical skills in the secondary school curriculum to achieve Vision 2025 in the Kilimanjaro region, Tanzania. This study found that strategies such as assigning learners practical skill activities, developing practical skill projects, for example, an individual learning method, and fostering a positive perception of teachers and learners towards practical skills, as well as an interlink between practical skills and employment opportunities. This could help the secondary school curriculum achieve and implement competence-based education.

Additionally, Anna et al. (2023) demonstrate that library instruction is typically conducted in the form of individual sessions. Teaching strategies used by librarians include flipped classroom, faux flip, classroom teaching, research clinics, consultations, and asynchronous learning. These teaching strategies enhanced engagement and relationships between students and librarians, while positively impacting critical thinking, confidence, and self-directed learning. Librarians should consider adopting and combining teaching strategies tailored to individual needs, utilizing technology to enhance teaching effectiveness and promote student learning. Therefore, individual learning methods, as a library resource strategy, could be employed to enhance competence-based education.

Project-Based Learning Method

Project-based learning represents an ideological framework and a particular approach to conducting class research or studies (Munisi, 2017). The term project-based learning is synonymous with problem-based learning. Students work on projects, such as community and design projects, and are expected to manage the projects or at least propose actions or solutions. Project-based learning, also known as problem-based learning, directs students to study a particular theme, idea, scenario, case, question, or problem that is less extensive than a project (Munisi, 2017; Tang, 2023). Students are responsible for the inquiry process over a specified period, guided or facilitated by a teacher. Since the project-based learning method is hands-on, primarily emergent, and evolutionary, focusing on various fields, the knowledge, skills, and dispositions that students gain are transferable to situations beyond the school context (Munisi, 2017; Tang, 2023). The curriculum provides ample space to improve students' critical thinking skills through flexible learning, focusing on students, and closely related to the context. Effective strategies include project-based learning, collaborative problem solving, and technology integration in the learning process (Iwan et al., 2024).

In particular, the researchers observed that students were given a specific task requiring them to search for materials on the tablets available in the library. Librarians guided these students in searching for materials and encouraged them to continue their studies. Additionally, the researchers

noted that Form Four students were tasked with preparing project proposals for gardening, taking into account the school environment. Through this process, students reviewed various library materials and shared ideas in groups before writing the project proposals assigned to them. For this reason, the project-based learning method could also be an important strategy for library resources in CBE.

Regarding individual learning and project-based learning methods as a student-centered approach to develop critical thinking skills, reinforce the importance of utilizing library resources, and foster a culture of independent learning among students (Anna et al., 2023; Mustafiyanti et al., 2023). Furthermore, a study by Rahman et al. (2024) supports the importance of using a student-centered approach to teaching and learning in microteaching, as it enhances knowledge, creativity, independent work, collaboration, and effective communication key components of critical thinking skills. Moreover, there is a need for modernized tools in the library, including computers that enable students and teachers to access online teaching and learning materials. This enables teachers to access current materials. Thus, schools ensure students make effective use of school libraries, current and sufficient library information resources should be facilitated establish better accommodation facilities, employ qualified school librarians to manage libraries including direct students on how to use library resources, and create a more conducive reading environment (Kanwera et al., 2024; Sakhrekar et al., 2023; Benard & Dulle, 2014).

According to Munisi (2017), the discussed methods that is individual learning and project-based leaning make students to become: comfortable and interested in their work, experience a sense of accomplishment in their daily life, become active in the learning process, opportunity for creativity and self-expressions are provided, a sense of responsibility and cooperation among students is fostered, and transformed students positive attitudes towards their thinking abilities that they are able. This aligns with the curriculum for secondary education (I-IV), which encourages teachers to use individual and group work, face-to-face questioning, and brainstorming various concepts (MoEST, 2023b). In addition, the discussions on the study results align with Section 3.6.4 of the ETP 2014 (2023) Edition, which states that teaching-learning resources, as tools, are essential in schools to promote a culture of reading and strengthen library services, as well as alternative knowledge acquisition methods (MoEST, 2023a).

Nevertheless, the Social Constructivism theory also supports the idea that students' engagement in various activities, both individually and as groups, enables them to perform better. Thus, the integration of available library resources and the methods used in teaching and learning influences students to become competent and apply what they have learned (Nino, 2023; Vygotsky, 1999).

Library Management Practices

The study findings emerged with sub-themes that focus on the practices of library management, which were identified as strategies that enhance the use of library resources for CBE. These strategies include the availability and proper utilization of library facilities, as well as effective time management. The library, as a treasured house of knowledge, needs to manage its resources effectively to provide quality services. The sub-themes are hereby discussed.

Availability and Utilization of Library Facilities

From the findings, the researchers observed that the Form One students were discussing and sharing ideas from the English Language students' book prepared by the TIE. Form One students were studying how to use ICT tools to search for information. The researchers observed that these textbooks are very communicative. This is because they include photos, instructions, questions, and explanations that can help students learn more effectively.

This fact has been emphasized by Bernard and Dulle (2014), who note that secondary school students effectively utilize school libraries. Therefore, it is essential to provide current and sufficient library information resources and establish better accommodations for digital facilities. According to Kanwera et al. (2024), schools should prioritize the expansion and modernization of their library facilities. This includes investing in a diverse collection of scientific literature, available in both print and digital formats, to cater to the varied learning needs of students. For this reason, secondary schools should implement a structured program that integrates library services into the curriculum for studying various subjects.

The study's findings are also supported by the ETP 2014 (2023). Section 3.6.4 states that the efficient implementation of curricula depends on the availability of appropriate teaching and learning resources and tools tailored to the needs of subjects and programs at different levels of education and training. These resources include high-quality textbooks, laboratory equipment, and tools to meet the curriculum's needs (MoEST, 2023a). In the same line of thought, Mubofu and Malekani (2019) indicate that the general idea for school libraries is to intensify the quality of education in schools through the provision of adequate facilities such as chairs, tables, textbooks, and qualified library staff to guide students in the appropriate usage of libraries for better performance.

The above discussion indicates that the schools involved in the study acknowledged that the available libraries are equipped with books and ICT facilities. To start with, such a library is preferable to having nothing at all. Some existing equipment, tools, and materials do not meet current needs. However, given the rapid pace of scientific and technological development, our school libraries need to be equipped with modern library facilities.

Time Management

In schools, it is essential to utilize library resources effectively. The process of utilizing these resources must be timely and well-managed so that library resources become effective (Bodkhe & Tanwar, 2021). The researchers observed that all five schools involved in this study have libraries and librarians. In these schools, the timetable for library sessions is posted on the notice board, indicating the time allocated for different classes to use the library. Additionally, the researchers reviewed the school timetable to determine the students' library sessions. Thus, time is a valuable resource, as it enhances the effectiveness of other resources (Sagimo, 2011). Time management gears other libraries as a valuable resource, as it enables resource strategies to enhance CBE.

The findings align with those of Mubofu and Malekani (2019) in Tanzania, where school libraries are described as the second classroom for students due to their significant role in enhancing the quality of education. The general idea for school libraries is to intensify the quality of education in schools through provision of adequate facilities such as chairs, tables, textbooks and qualified library staff to guide students in

appropriate usage of libraries for better performance and this implied that school are emphasize students to use the library through school timetable library sessions which facilitates the use of library resources to enhance CBE.

Similarly, Enda et al. (2020) demonstrate that effective time management in learning activities leads to students' learning tasks becoming more organized, more enjoyable, and enables them to perform unexpected tasks more effectively and on time. This means that the practical implications of effective time management in learning yield regular, pleasant results, and flexibility can be achieved by considering strategies and mastering information technology. The results align with ETP 2014 (2023) Edition, Section 3.6.4, which states that it is essential to have an efficient system for preparing, printing, and distributing all teaching and learning materials (MoEST, 2023a). For this reason, there is also a need to promote a culture of reading and strengthen library services, as well as alternative knowledge acquisition methods, through effective time management, as stated in subsection 3.6.4.6 of the ETP 2014 (2023) Edition.

The findings support that a daily schedule or timetable assists in managing library resources in various ways, such as: allocation of a reasonable number of students who are to use the library, identification of enough and available materials needed at a particular time, allocation of library staff for supervision, and enhances self-preparations among teachers and students before going to the library.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

The ELCT ND Secondary schools in Hai District are commended for adhering to the ETP 2014 (2023) Edition, particularly in providing and enhancing library resource strategies for CBE. Observation was made that most libraries are neither equipped with modern facilities nor managed by library systems. This situation should not hinder the existing libraries from continuing to operate as the schools renovate or design new ones. Thus, the student-centric approach to teaching and learning, combined with social-interactive library management practices, supports the effective use of library resources.

6.2 Recommendation

The positive utilization of strategies is recommended for library users and library management practices to accommodate modern changes. Therefore, library management strategies should be in place and implemented to ensure that school libraries accommodate both the pace of science and technology, as well as the needs for general studies and vocational studies education pathways, in the current practices of the country's education system. This is because library resources play a significant role in expanding knowledge, skills, and fostering positive attitudes towards educational practices. For further study, the researchers recommend that a similar study be conducted using a quantitative approach or a mixed-methods approach, allowing the results to be quantified and analyzed. This will help in understanding the reality of the quality and quantity of secondary schools' libraries available, as well as the resources needed to enhance the implementation of competence-based education.

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